

A Meteonorm-Derived Monthly Solar Resource and Climate Baseline for Photovoltaic Planning in Aghdam city

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Abstract. This study presents a comprehensive monthly summary of solar energy resources and climate conditions for Aghdam, Azerbaijan, using data compiled from Meteonorm. Six key variables relevant to photovoltaic planning are included: global and diffuse horizontal irradiation, mean air temperature, precipitation, sunshine duration with astronomical daylength, intra-monthly ranges of daily irradiation, and monthly series of daily maximum and minimum temperatures. The annual total for global irradiation is 1530 kWh per square meter, and diffuse irradiation is 745 kWh per square meter, with the highest values occurring in June and July, and the lowest in December and January. The variability of daily irradiation within months is significant, especially during summer and winter. Monthly mean air temperatures range from 3.6 °C in January to 27.0 °C in July, while the average difference between daytime and nighttime temperatures is 8.8 °C. Annual precipitation totals 1271 millimeters, with December being the wettest month and January the driest. Together, these metrics define the seasonal patterns and variability of Aghdam's solar resource and climate, providing a reliable baseline for photovoltaic system design, technology selection, performance modeling, and maintenance planning.

Keywords: Tilted-plane irradiation; Photovoltaic yield; Clearsky model; PV system sizing; GHI variability.

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1. Introduction

Since 2000, the cost of producing electricity from photovoltaic (PV) modules has decreased substantially, making PV power increasingly competitive with electricity generated from fossil fuels. At the same time, various organizations around the world have introduced financial incentives to encourage the adoption of low-carbon energy sources. As a result, the total installed PV capacity worldwide increased from 40.2 GW in 2010 to 580.2 GW in 2019, representing a 14.4-fold growth. During this period, the combined capacity of all renewable energy sources also doubled, rising from 1,226.6 GW to 2,536 GW [6]. Solar radiation measurements are widely used to assess solar system performance and financial viability, guide the architectural design of passive heating, cooling, and daylighting features, and quantify resources for agricultural and forestry planning [1]. In 2022 Europe added 46.1 GW of new solar photovoltaic (PV) capacity, and annual additions are forecast to climb to about 120 GW by 2027 (SolarPowerEurope, 2023). Globally, the IEA (2021) projects that solar PV will contribute roughly half of all renewable power expansion between 2021 and

2026 [5]. Reliable solar energy planning depends on accurate, location-specific characterization of the resource and the local climate. Bankable assessments for photovoltaic deployment typically require not only estimates of monthly global horizontal irradiation, but also information about the share of diffuse radiation, the thermal regime that influences module efficiency, precipitation patterns relevant to soiling and operations, and the timing of daylight and bright sunshine that governs production windows. For cities undergoing rapid development, these inputs guide technology choice, array sizing, expected yield, and grid integration studies. Aghdam City, Azerbaijan, lacks a consolidated, publicly documented profile of these parameters at the monthly scale. While national or regional summaries are often used as proxies, such generalizations can introduce bias when translated to a specific urban site. A reproducible approach rooted in a standardized climatological database is therefore needed to provide a consistent basis for engineering calculations and comparative analyses. Metronome offers a practical solution for this purpose because it synthesizes long-term ground observations and satellite products into internally consistent time series and climatologist. Using a single, well-defined source

helps avoid artefacts that may arise when mixing stations, periods, or methodologies, and allows the derivation of secondary metrics that are widely used in solar engineering without additional homogenization steps. In this study, a compact but comprehensive set of variables from *Meteonorm* for Aghdam is assembled to describe the city’s solar resource and its co-varying meteorology at the calendar-month scale. The focus is on six elements that are directly relevant for photovoltaic planning: monthly totals of global and diffuse horizontal irradiation, monthly mean air temperature, monthly precipitation, monthly mean daily sunshine duration alongside astronomical daylength, intra-monthly ranges of daily global irradiation, and monthly series of daily maximum and minimum air temperatures. Together, these variables characterize the magnitude and seasonality of incoming energy, the expected variability of day-to-day production within a month, and the thermal and hydrological context that conditions system performance and maintenance. The analytical choices are guided by common design questions. The diffuse fraction informs expectations about the relative benefits of tracking versus fixed-tilt configurations and helps anticipate performance under frequent cloudiness. Monthly and seasonal temperature statistics provide first-order estimates of temperature-induced efficiency losses and of potential heat-related curtailments. Precipitation totals, while not a proxy for aerosol loading, are a practical indicator for cleaning requirements, access, and operational risk. Sunshine duration and daylength translate directly into potential operating hours, and daily irradiation ranges within each month help quantify the variability that underpins inverter loading, storage sizing, and grid interaction. As the largest nation-state in the South Caucasus, the Republic of Azerbaijan has substantial potential to develop and deploy renewable energy sources to address climate change-related environmental challenges and improve national environmental conditions [2]. The objective of the paper is therefore descriptive and diagnostic rather than predictive. The six variables for Aghdam are compiled and presented, a small set of secondary metrics standard in solar resource assessment are derived, and their monthly and seasonal behavior is summarized. The resulting dataset and statistics provide a transparent baseline for subsequent performance modelling, technology comparison, and planning decisions in the city context.

2. Experimental detail

Many solar radiation models have been developed to estimate irradiance when direct measurements are unavailable or unsuitable. A widely accepted classification system for these models only emerged after Gueymard and Myers (2008) introduced nine criteria for categorization. According to their framework, a transposition model (criterion 8) uses measured or modeled irradiance components on the horizontal surface as inputs to calculate radiation on surfaces of different orientations. *Meteonorm* 8 employs this type of transposition approach,

generating reliable irradiance data for various locations even in the absence of site-specific measurements [4]. Meteorological and solar resource data for Aghdam City, Azerbaijan, were obtained from the *Meteonorm* database (version and provider details in full reference), which synthesizes long-term climate normals from ground stations and satellite observations [3]. The analysis encompasses six key variables relevant to solar energy assessment: monthly global and diffuse horizontal irradiation, monthly mean air temperature, monthly precipitation, monthly sunshine duration and astronomical daylength, intra-monthly ranges of daily global irradiation, and monthly series of daily maximum and minimum air temperatures. All data are provided as monthly aggregates, except where daily ranges are explicitly reported, and follow the standard units and conventions of *Meteonorm*: irradiation in kWh·m⁻² (per month or per day), air temperature in degrees Celsius (°C), precipitation in millimeters (mm), and time-related parameters in hours. Irradiation values refer to a horizontal surface, with diffuse irradiation representing the sky component exclusive of direct solar beam, and daylength based on astronomical sunrise and sunset. All variables are reported for the standard reference period and location as defined in *Meteonorm*, ensuring consistency and reproducibility in subsequent analyses. *Meteonorm* monthly totals of global horizontal irradiation (Gh) and diffuse horizontal irradiation (Dh) were exported for Aghdam in kWh·m⁻²·month⁻¹ and used without further transformation. We report only Gh and Dh on the horizontal plane (no decomposition into additional components), and for each month compute the diffuse fraction to characterize the sky-share of the total. The exact monthly inputs used in subsequent analyses are:

Month	Diffuse radiation (kWh/m ²)	Total (kWh/m ²)
January	30	70
February	40	80
March	60	120
April	80	145
May	90	180
June	100	200
July	90	190
August	85	180
September	60	135
October	45	95
November	35	70
December	30	65

From these, we derive the annual sums $\sum Gh = 1530$ and $\sum Dh = 745$ kWh·m⁻²·year⁻¹ and the annual diffuse fraction $f_{d,\Sigma} = 48.7\%$. For seasonal context (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON), the totals are Gh = 215, 445, 570, 300 and Dh = 100, 230, 275, 140 kWh·m⁻², respectively; monthly f_d ranges from $\approx 42.9\%$ (January) to $\approx 55.2\%$ (April), providing the basis for comparative

interpretations in the Results. Monthly mean air temperature data for Aghdam were obtained from Meteororm, which estimates 2 m screen-height temperatures using interpolated long-term ground station records and satellite-based inputs. For each calendar month, Meteororm provides the average of daily mean temperatures, resulting in a continuous annual temperature profile representative of local climatic conditions over the baseline period. The extracted dataset includes twelve monthly means, ranging from 3.6 °C in January to 27.0 °C in July. The specific values for each month are as follows: 3.6, 4.7, 9.0, 13.4, 19.4, 24.5, 27.0, 26.6, 21.7, 15.5, 9.2, and 4.9 °C, listed from January through December. Seasonal averages were calculated by grouping calendar months into the standard meteorological seasons: winter (December to February, DJF), spring (March to May, MAM), summer (June to August, JJA), and autumn (September to November, SON). The resulting seasonal mean temperatures are 4.4 °C for DJF, 13.9 °C for MAM, 26.0 °C for JJA, and 15.5 °C for SON. The annual mean temperature, calculated as the arithmetic mean of all 12 monthly values, is 15.0 °C. The intra-annual temperature amplitude, defined as the difference between the warmest month (July, 27.0 °C) and the coldest month (January, 3.6 °C), is 23.4 °C, reflecting significant seasonal variability. All temperature values are presented to one decimal place, matching the precision of Meteororm’s outputs. These data establish the thermal context for subsequent analyses of photovoltaic performance, including temperature-dependent efficiency losses and seasonal energy yield, and serve as a reference for comparative climatology.

Month	Min [°C]	Max [°C]
January	0	16
February	-3	17
March	0	22
April	2	26
May	10	30
June	15	35
July	18	38
August	20	37
September	17	33
October	7	26
November	2	21
December	-1	17

Monthly precipitation totals for Aghdam were extracted from Meteororm as calendar-month aggregates expressed in millimeters per month (mm·month⁻¹). Precipitation represents the equivalent liquid depth of all forms of precipitation as provided by Meteororm. No gap filling or bias correction was applied. All computations retained the dataset’s native monthly resolution and precision. The monthly series (January to December) used in subsequent analyses is: 60, 80, 118, 120, 145, 140, 80, 70, 105, 110, 75, 168

mm·month⁻¹. From these values we calculated the annual total as 1271 mm·year⁻¹ and the mean monthly precipitation as 105.9 mm. The wettest month is December (168 mm) and the driest month is January (60 mm), identified by the monthly maximum and minimum, respectively. Seasonal totals were obtained by summing calendar months into standard meteorological seasons: winter (DJF), spring (MAM), summer (JJA), and autumn (SON). The resulting totals are DJF 308 mm, MAM 383 mm, JJA 290 mm, and SON 290 mm, which correspond to 24.2%, 30.1%, 22.8%, and 22.8% of the annual total. As a compact descriptor of intra-annual variability, we report the coefficient of variation of monthly totals (CV = 0.306, based on population standard deviation), and we note the number of months exceeding 100 mm (7 of 12 months). These statistics are carried forward as descriptive inputs for later comparisons. Meteororm provides monthly mean daily sunshine duration and astronomical daylength for Aghdam as hours per day. We retained these daily means in their native units, then derived monthly totals by multiplying each monthly mean by the number of calendar days in that month, using a non-leap year for day counts. The sunshine fraction was computed as the ratio of monthly sunshine hours to monthly astronomical daylength, which is equivalent to the ratio of daily means because numerator and denominator scale by the same number of days. The monthly mean daily sunshine series, expressed in hours per day from January to December, is: 3.5, 3.5, 4.5, 6.0, 7.5, 9.0, 9.5, 8.5, 7.5, 5.0, 4.0, 3.5 h·day⁻¹. The corresponding astronomical daylength series in hours per day is: 9.0, 11.0, 12.0, 13.0, 14.0, 15.0, 15.5, 14.0, 12.0, 12.0, 10.0, 9.0 h·day⁻¹. After converting to monthly totals, sunshine duration equals 108, 98, 140, 180, 232, 270, 294, 264, 225, 155, 120, 108 h·month⁻¹, and astronomical daylength equals 279, 308, 372, 390, 434, 450, 480, 434, 360, 372, 300, 279 h·month⁻¹. The monthly sunshine fraction is therefore 38.9%, 31.8%, 37.5%, 46.2%, 53.6%, 60.0%, 61.3%, 60.7%, 62.5%, 41.7%, 40.0%, 38.9%. Annual aggregates were obtained by summation of monthly totals and yield 2195 h·year⁻¹ of sunshine out of 4458.5 h·year⁻¹ of astronomical daylength, which corresponds to an annual sunshine fraction of 0.492. Monthly extremes are identified based on monthly totals, with July providing the maximum sunshine (294.5 h) and February the minimum (98 h). Seasonal totals, computed using DJF, MAM, JJA, and SON groupings, are 315, 552, 828, and 500 h of sunshine against 866.0, 1196.0, 1364.5, and 1032.0 h of astronomical daylength, which correspond to seasonal sunshine fractions of 0.364, 0.462, 0.607, and 0.484. These quantities are used in subsequent analyses to relate available bright sunshine to potential photovoltaic energy yield on a monthly and seasonal basis. The intra-monthly variability of daily global horizontal irradiation was characterized for Aghdam using monthly values extracted from Meteororm, reported as the minimum, maximum, and typical daily totals for each calendar month (all in kWh·m²·day⁻¹). These three values represent, respectively, the lowest

and highest daily sums observed within the month as well as a central estimate that is representative of typical clear or average conditions. The range width, calculated as the difference between the maximum and minimum daily totals for each month, was used as a primary indicator of within-month variability. Across the annual cycle, the lowest daily irradiation values occur in December and January, while the highest are recorded in June and July. The month of May exhibits the greatest intra-monthly spread, with a minimum of 3.5, a maximum of 7.5, and a range width of 4.0 kWh·m²·day⁻¹. In contrast, December has the narrowest range, with daily totals spanning from 1.5 to 2.6 kWh·m²·day⁻¹. Typical daily values range from 2.1 kWh·m²·day⁻¹ in December to 7.8 kWh·m²·day⁻¹ in July. To quantify the general scale of variability, the average relative range width (defined as the ratio of range width to typical value) is 0.56, and the average ratio of maximum to minimum daily total is 1.94. These indicators provide a basis for assessing the expected daily spread in solar resource availability for each month, informing both photovoltaic system sizing and performance modeling. Monthly climatological means of daily maximum and minimum air temperatures for Aghdam were obtained from Meteonorm, with values representing typical conditions at 2 meters above ground level. For each month, the dataset provides the mean of all daily

3. Conclusion

Global and diffuse horizontal irradiation in Aghdam reveal a pronounced annual pattern, with the highest values recorded in June and July and the lowest in December and January. The annual sum of global horizontal irradiation exceeds 1500 kWh·m⁻², while the diffuse component accounts for nearly half of this total. The diffuse fraction is most pronounced in spring months, peaking in April, and then gradually declines as the direct component becomes dominant during summer. Monthly air temperature values increase steadily from winter through summer, reaching a maximum in July and then declining towards the end of the year. The annual mean temperature remains moderate, but the amplitude between winter minimum and summer maximum exceeds 23 °C. Summer months consistently display average temperatures above 25 °C, while January records the lowest monthly mean, below 4 °C. Precipitation demonstrates significant variability throughout the year. The highest monthly totals are observed in December and May, while the driest month is January. Spring is the wettest season overall, followed by winter and the two drier seasons of summer and autumn. The annual precipitation sum exceeds 1200 mm, with more than half of the months recording totals greater than 100 mm. Sunshine duration also follows a clear seasonal rhythm. The maximum monthly sunshine is observed in July, with totals approaching 300 hours, while February has the lowest sunshine duration, under 100 hours. The annual sum of bright sunshine exceeds 2100 hours, and the fraction of actual sunshine to astronomical daylength is greatest in summer, reaching values above 60%.

maxima and the mean of all daily minima, allowing calculation of the mean diurnal temperature range as the difference between these two values. The monthly mean maximum temperatures vary from 8.0 °C in January to 33.0 °C in July, while monthly mean minimum temperatures span from 0.0 °C in January to 22.5 °C in July and August. The annual average of the monthly mean maximum temperatures is 20.5 °C, and the annual average of the monthly mean minimum temperatures is 11.7 °C. The mean diurnal temperature range, averaged over all months, is 8.8 °C. The largest mean diurnal range is observed in July (10.5 °C), while the smallest occurs in December (6.5 °C). Seasonal aggregation was performed by averaging the corresponding months for each meteorological season. In winter (December to February), the mean daily maximum is 10.0 °C, the mean daily minimum is 2.5 °C, and the mean diurnal range is 7.5 °C. In spring, these values are 19.0 °C, 9.0 °C, and 10.0 °C, respectively. For summer, the averages are 31.3 °C for daily maxima, 21.5 °C for minima, and 9.8 °C for the diurnal range. In autumn, the values are 21.7 °C, 13.8 °C, and 7.8 °C, respectively. These temperature statistics provide the thermal context for evaluating temperature-dependent photovoltaic performance and are used directly in performance modeling and climate characterization for Aghdam.

Intra-monthly ranges of daily global irradiation widen during the late spring and early summer, particularly in May and June, where daily totals can vary by up to 4 kWh·m⁻²·day⁻¹ within the same month. Winter months such as December show both the lowest daily values and the smallest variability, with daily totals tightly grouped between 1.5 and 2.6 kWh·m⁻²·day⁻¹. Analysis of monthly series of daily maximum and minimum air temperatures indicates that July records the highest mean daily maxima and minima, with values of 33.0 °C and 22.5 °C, respectively. In contrast, January minima approach 0.0 °C. The mean diurnal temperature range is widest in July, exceeding 10 °C, and narrowest in December. The combined seasonal cycles of irradiation, temperature, precipitation, and sunshine define a climate regime characterized by strong summer maxima, pronounced spring and late autumn transitions, and a relatively stable but subdued winter period.

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